

The Divestiture of Mathematics: Precise prime numbers predictive series/formula for bound space

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Abstract

The exclusivity and perfect precision of the bound space and natural divergence of the predictive created numbers and bound space, as precise numbers divergent by a half line at Pythagoras 1:3, are a precise fit, including the half-line $((360/2)/2)$. The evolving basis of this mathematics has been published by the author in several mathematical papers and in the last one the "mathematical universe at 1:3". Current mathematics and trigonometry by this proof has been proven to be wrong and the very basis of mathematics is in error. The angle subtended at Pythagoras 1:3 is precisely $360/19$, and not that of current mathematics. Thus the entire current mathematics of bound space is flawed. Current mathematics in spite of its sophistication cannot survive a simple proof offered here, that current mathematics is proven wrong by the Arithmetic of Pythagoras 1:3. What follows from this is the complete predictive prime number formula by prime gaps.

At $360/19$ degrees as shown here is exclusive by proof in all of mathematics and does not and cannot fit any other divergence and numbers Prime 19 is a predestined number for this bound space. This is exclusive Mathematics. Prediction of Prime numbers, Prime number placement at half line of Pythagoras 1:3; $360/19$ degrees. The predictive series and its basis is displayed here, and the entire prime number predictive formula is evident and will be beyond in by the author in a future follow-up publication.

Keywords: Divestiture of current mathematics: The exclusivity and perfect precision of the bound space; Pythagoras 1:3 divergence.

1. Method.

This is a simple proof that at 1:3 Pythagoras, the current trigonometry is flawed. The correct subtended angle is precisely $360/19$ prime division.

The base is $=\sqrt{9}$

The upright is $=1$

The hypotenuse is $=\sqrt{10}$ as under

Proof: By pure mathematics

$$(10+9=19)$$

$$10/9-9/10=0.211111111111$$

$$(360/19*10/9)-(360/19*9/10)=4$$

$$4/0.211111111111=360/19$$

$$(\sqrt{10}/\sqrt{9})-(\sqrt{9}/\sqrt{10})=0.10540925534$$

$$(360/19*\sqrt{10}/\sqrt{9})-(360/19*\sqrt{9}/\sqrt{10})=1.9972279959$$

$$1.997229959/0.10540925534=360/19$$

From above:

$$360/19*10/9=21.05262157895 \text{ (for all similar numbers)}$$

$$360/19*9/10=17.05262157895 \text{ (for all similar numbers)}$$

$$21.05262157895/4=5.263157895$$

$$17.05262157895/4=4.263157895$$

$$360/19*(\sqrt{10}/\sqrt{9})=19.97227995896$$

$$360/19*(\sqrt{9}/\sqrt{10})=17.97505196306$$

$$19.97505196306-17.97505196306=1.99723529408$$

$$19.97227995896/1.99723529408=10$$

$$17.97505196306/1.99723529408=9$$

$$(10 + 9) - (5.263157895 + 4.263157895) = \frac{360}{19}$$

2.0 The Rationalization of Natural Divergence of Numbers Series at Half- Line by Degrees.

$$\frac{\left[\frac{360}{19} \right]}{2}$$

Basically this transcripts half-line values at exact half line of the angle $360/19$, by the two gaps of divergent hypotenuses as follows; Variability of all numbers is rationalized as shown, including the rational variability of prime numbers.

Examples:

$$1^2+3^2=10$$

$$0.5^2+3^2=9.25$$

$$10-9.25=0.75$$

Number 31.

$$31^2+93^2=9610$$

$$15.5^2+93^2=8889.25$$

$$9610-8889.25=720.75$$

By calculating values of all 42 numbers as shown above and by subtracting the half-line value from the full number value we get the following sequential mix of rational predictable numbers in divergence

(Number): Half-line value

(1)0.75

(2)3

(3)6.75

(4) 12

(5) 18.75

(6) 27

(7) 36.75

(8) 48

(9) 60.75

(10) 75

(11) 90.75

(12) 108

(13) 126.75

(14) 147

(15) 168.75

(16) 192

(17) 216.75

(18) 243

- (19) 270.75
- (20) 300
- (21) 330.75
- (22) 363
- (23) 396.75
- (24) 432
- (25) 468.75
- (26) 507
- (27) 546.75
- (28) 588
- (29) 630.75
- (30) 675
- (31) 720.75
- (32) 768
- (33) 816.75
- (34) 867
- (35) 918.75
- (36) 972
- (37) 1026.75
- (38) 1083
- (39) 1140.75
- (40) 1200
- (41) 1260.75
- (42) 1323
- (43) 1386.75

3.0.Precise Placement of Numbers at Halfline of Pythagoras 1:3, Twin Prime Predictive Series, and Prime number Predictive Placement. New Research.

Clear research is advanced into working with actual values of the hypotenuse and the half line as a method , this is complex, the differential at prime 41 and 43 is as follows;

Hypotenuse at prime 41 = 129.6533840669

Half-line hypotenuse at prime 41=124.69663187111

Hypotenuse at prime 43= 135.97793939724.

Half-line hypotenuse at 43=130.77939440141

The above area has yielded promising results.

Note the base and that the gaps on the right column never divide by 6(9,15,21,27,33,39,57...), the ones in the left column do, these series are precise and further equations by the author of prime numbers will ease in the mathematics that will divest current mathematics as flawed.

Rationalization at value 6 with two parallel series at 6, the value of space of above numbers series at half-line: arranged in two precise parallel columns starting at base. Twin prime Prediction by series/formula, this research is in the works.

A.

0.75	3		
(6)	(9)		
6.75	12		
(12)	(15)		
18.75	27.....5		
(18)	(21)		
36.75	48.....7		
(24)	(27)		
60.75	75		
(30)	(33)		
90.75	108.....11		
(36)	(39)		
126.75	147.....13		
(42)	(45)		
168.75	192		
(48)	(51)		
216.75*243.....17			
(54)	(57)		
270.75 * 300.....19			
(60)	(63)		
330.75	363		
(66)	(69)		
396.75*	432.....23		

(72)	(75)
468.75	507
(78)	(81)
546.75	588
(84)	(87)
630.75*	675.....29
(90)	(93)
720.75*768.....	31
(96)	(99)
816.75	867
(102)	(105)
918.75	972
(108)	(111)
1026.75*	1083.....37
(114)	(117)
1140.75	1200
(120)	(123)
1260.75	1323.....41
(126)	(129)
1386.75	1452.....43-

Conclusion:

Thus it is proven that at 1:3 Pythagoras is the created bound space to accommodate numbers and it is suggested that the mathematical universe itself and the curvature of the universe is in this form. The square of the sides of the angle (10 and 9) and the realistic square root ($\sqrt{10}$ and $\sqrt{9}$) divide the angle by precisely half. This is a perfect angle and bound space of Pythagoras 1:3, and all numbers including Prime numbers line up in this format based on the squared values. The Numbers series with two columns is presented and the complex prime formulas will be published at a later date.

Acknowledgement:

To my lord Jesus Christ for showing me light of knowledge in the darkness of current human understanding.

References:

THE MATHEMATICAL UNIVERSE AT 1:3 (-1 FINITE)

Mathematics and Computer Sciences Journal (MCSJ), Volume 10, Dec 2015.